

COST VS BENEFIT: THE CASE OF KENYA CLEAN COOKING

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Kenya has about 70% of the households using traditional biomass fuels with three-stone open fire for cooking. This negatively impacts the health, increase the emissions and impacts the social and economic well-being of the households. About 23,000 deaths in Kenya have been linked to indoor air pollution.

This study investigated the economic, health, environmental, and time-saving benefits of clean cooking technologies in Kenya using the OnStove modelling tool (Net-benefit modelling tool). The analysis explored three scenarios: private (household), social cost-benefit analysis, and a custom scenario based on national targets (stove-shares).

The results indicate that Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) offers the highest net benefit in the social and custom stove share scenario. The private scenario indicates net benefit from the biomass forced draft with negative health benefits. The overall net benefit from LPG are from health savings, opportunity cost and emission reductions. Access to clean cooking remains inequitable due to affordability and infrastructure gaps.

The study recommends targeted subsidies, infrastructure expansion, and awareness campaigns to drive adoption of LPG, electricity, and ethanol cookstoves in underserved communities.

INTRODUCTION

The Sub-Saharan region still lags in access to clean cooking energy as over 900 million people still rely on firewood, charcoal and other polluting fuel (IEA, 2022). The use of dirty fuels contributes to health, environmental and social impacts and also affects women and children directly due to long hours of fuel collection, exposure to injury and harm, as well exposure to the indoor air pollution (PM2.5) (WHO, 2021). Kenya's population as at 2024 was 51,525,585 (urban 16,374,954 and rural 35,150,632) with 13,886,126 households of which 61.4% and 38.6% in rural and urban areas respectively (KNBS, 2024) In Kenya, over 70% of the rural households still rely on traditional biomass, contributing to indoor air pollution, forest degradation, and time poverty. About 23,000 death annually are linked to indoor pollution (MoH, 2021).

Access to clean cooking energy directly contributes to progress on several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land). Despite regional commitments, including the African Union's Agenda 2063, and National targets outlined in Vision 2030, the rate of clean cooking access has not kept pace with electrification progress.

Kenya projects that at least 50% of the households will use LPG, 30% bioethanol, 10% electric cooking, 3% biogas and 7% Other (Low emission clean burning sustainable biomass) by 2030 (MoEP, 2024). This study uses the OnStove tool to evaluate net benefits of key clean cooking technologies and inform policy interventions. The OnStove modelling tool is a spatial, net benefit tool, that quantifies and compares the economic, health, environmental, and time-saving benefits of different clean cooking options. The study quantified the net benefits of LPG, Biogas, Electric cooking, bioethanol, charcoal ICS, collected biomass among other technologies and determined their net benefit in private (household) and social (Community/ national) scenarios. The findings aim to inform national policy and contribute to Kenya's goals of achieving universal access to modern energy services by 2030, in line with SDG 7.

Research Questions

- What are the net benefits of clean cookstoves from a private household perspective?
- What are the net benefits from a national social scenario?

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- How do stove share targets under KNCTS impact costs and benefits?

Objectives:

1. Determine the net benefit of the clean cookstoves base on private scenarios
2. Determine the net benefit of the clean cookstoves base on social scenarios
3. Determine the net benefit from the custom scenario base on stove shares (social scenario)

METHODOLOGY

Modelling Approach

The process for the cost benefit analysis (CBA) includes: explaining the purpose, identifying alternatives, deciding on how the costs are counted, identify impact categories, predict the impacts, monetize impacts, discount costs and benefits to present value, determine net present value of each alternative, perform a sensitivity analysis and make recommendations. The process of analysis includes: data input, GIS processing, baseline calibration and net- benefit calculations.

Data Sources

1. Kenya National Cooking Transition Strategy (KNCTS, 2024)
2. Kenya Demographic and health Survey Report (2024)

Assumptions

1. Electric Pressure Cooker (EPC) was considered in the analysis and allocated investment cost of \$115.38
2. Biogas cost of 10m³ digester approx. \$1154
3. LPG stove cost at \$15.38 for 6kg cylinder in the social scenario and \$26.92 for private scenario
4. The transitions apply to both rural and urban

Scenarios

1. Private scenarios modelling for biogas, biomass forced draft, LPG, ethanol, E-Cooking, traditional charcoal, traditional biomass, and pellets forced draft technologies including impacts on costs, health, time and environment. – using current data
2. Social scenario- modelling for biogas, biomass forced draft, LPG, Ethanol, E-Cooking, traditional charcoal, traditional biomass, and pellets forced draft technologies including impacts on costs, health, time and environment. -using current data

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3. Social Scenario -Custom modelling using the projections in KNCTS (urban: Charcoal ICS: 0.10, LPG: 0.50, Electricity: 0.10, Ethanol: 0.30) and (Rural: Collected Improved Biomass: 0.0525, Charcoal ICS: 0.0175, LPG: 0.50, Electricity: 0.10, Biogas: 0.03, Ethanol:0.30)

RESULTS

1. Private Scenario OnStove Model

The highest net benefit from the private scenario was from biomass ICS and LPG with a stove share of 53% and 39% respectively. The high biomass ICS stove share contributed to low death avoided of 3139 pp/year and low health benefits of \$0.50 billion *Figure 1* . Biogas has low net benefit with high investment compared to any other technology. Charcoal ICS has a negative health effects with overall low cost and benefit compared to other fuels. The low net benefit in biogas and charcoal is due to the low stove share of 6% and 2% and the low usage among the population.

LPG has the highest net benefit in terms of health and emission reductions compared to biomass ICS FD and other fuels. LPG has a cost of about \$749.578 million (investment, fuel and OM cost) and net benefit of about \$1187.848 million, thus a better option for transiting to clean cooking due to the high net benefit. The population with low wealth index (poor) rely on biomass improved cookstoves forced draft (Biomass ICS FD) while those on the medium to high index use LPG.

Maximum net-benefit cooking technology

Figure 1: Net benefit private scenarios OnStove model

2. Social Scenario OnStove Model

The net benefit from the social scenario was from LPG with a stove share 89%. The high stove share of LPG resulted in higher number of death avoided of 10,871pp/year *Figure 2* compared to the private scenarios in *Figure 1*. This is also linked to the health costs avoided, where the social scenarios have a high health cost avoided (\$2.18 billion) compared to the private scenario (\$0.58 billion). Biogas has high net benefit compared to biomass and ethanol, with its use mainly in the low to middle wealth households.

LPG has the highest net benefit (cost of about \$2165.06 million (investment, fuel and OM cost) and net benefit of about \$ 2540.522million) to the other fuels. LPG a better option for transiting to clean cooking due to the high net benefit. The population with low wealth index (poor) mainly uses the biomass ICS FD while those on the medium to high index use LPG. Although biogas and electricity are clean cooking technologies the least allocation of clean cookstove shares. The maximum net benefit and total costs per households are highest where there are LPG and biogas, this is due to high stove shares in these areas *Figure 2*.

Maximum net-benefit cooking technology

Figure 2: Net Benefit Social Scenario OnStove Model

3. Social Scenario: Custom Stove Share Model

The social scenario modelling used the targets for the technologies based on the national projections in the KNCTS. The modelling analysis indicated that the maximum net benefit was from LPG with a cost of about \$ 1240.189 million (investment, fuel and OM cost) and net benefit of about \$ 1488.264 million. About of 50% of the population expected to use LPG across the country, while a total of the 8% expected to use charcoal ICS and biomass ICS ND Figure 3. Ethanol with a stove share of about 30% has a high fuel cost compared electricity (10% stove share) which indicates a high investment cost and low fuel cost. However, ethanol has a high net benefit compared to e-cooking.

The emissions avoided under the social scenarios are also high (about 47 MtCO₂) compared to the private scenario (about 36 MtCO₂), while the time saved for the households is high where there are high shares of clean cookstoves in the social scenario of 0.8 h/hh/day compared to private scenario 0.43 h/hh/day.

The households able to use LPG, ethanol and electricity are mostly in the middle and high relative wealth index level. The use of biomass and charcoal ICS are mostly in the low relative wealth index portion and the households in the high relative wealth index areas. Charcoal ICS

and biomass ICS have negative effects on health even though they show low to no fuel cost associated with them Figure 3. The total cost per household has increase for the custom scenario stove_shares due to the high investment cost of LPG, ethanol, and electricity Figure 4 compared to the private scenarios where biomass ICS has the highest share with low investment cost. The areas with high maximum net benefit also have the highest total costs per households

Figure 3: Social Custom Scenario modelling for Kenya- stove_shares

Figure 4: Maximum net benefit and total cost per household: Social Custom Scenario stove_shares and OnStove model

DISCUSSION

Charcoal ICS and Biomass ICS natural draft both have negative health benefits and when there is high stove share the death avoided are also low, this is because the biomass ICS is not a clean technology thus people are still exposed indoor air pollution and high levels of PM_{2.5}. The death avoided are low compared the report by the World Health Organization in the number of deaths per year of about 23,000 associated with lack of clean cooking (WHO, 2022). This implies the current situation where most of the population use biomass for cooking with three-stone open fire mostly in the rural areas and exposed to high levels of PM_{2.5}. The high health cost avoided in social scenario compared to private scenarios is attributed to the use of clean cookstoves characterized with low PM_{2.5}, thus reduced risk of respiratory diseases.

The emissions in the private scenario compared to social scenarios (both on OnStove and custom stove_shares) is attributed to the technology shares, the private scenario has a high % of biomass and charcoal stoves which are inefficient and have high emission rate compared to social scenarios where the highest shared are on LPG, ethanol and electricity. Thus, to achieve net-zero the promotion of clean cookstoves is critical for both rural and urban areas.

The low time saved in the private scenario is attributed to the time taken to look for fuel (distance walked for fuel collection, time for making a meal, technology efficiency). The clean cooking technologies have high time saved due to their efficiency, low time for cooking and fuel collection. This also relates the wealth index, where the population with low wealth index (poor) use charcoal and biomass ICS FD while those on the medium to high index use LPG and other clean cookstoves. The relation between time saved and fuel/ cookstove use indicate the poverty cycle associated with clean cooking, the less disadvantaged population spend more time in fuel collection that could have been spent in other productive usage in the economy. The use of biomass and charcoal ICS high relative wealth index areas calls for awareness creation and promotion of behaviour change in the households.

To achieve maximum net benefit on the death avoided, emissions, time saved and reduced health costs, the share of biomass and charcoal has to be very low <1%, thus, there is need to promote the use of clean cookstoves through awareness creation, subsidy on the investment and fuel costs for clean cookstoves.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Access to clean cooking remains a challenge to many households due to different factor including lack of awareness, affordability, accessibility, among other factors. The OnStove tool provides the modelling for net benefit, combining different data to show benefits and costs of the different technologies to the households. Affordability is one of the limiting factors due to the high investment and fuel cost of clean cookstoves (LPG, Ethanol and electric cooking). Thus, policies are needed to provide sustainable subsidies on both fuels and cookstoves in order to achieve net benefit as well as infrastructure development for both LPG and electricity. In general:

- LPG and electric cooking have the highest health, environmental, and time benefits.
- Poor households are disproportionately affected due to limited access to modern fuels.

The policy insights and recommendations from the analysis include:

- Introduce targeted subsidies for clean cookstoves and fuels (LPG, EPC, ethanol)
- Expand LPG and electricity infrastructure, especially in rural areas
- Launch nationwide awareness campaigns on health impacts of biomass

The Future work should consider the following:

- Research on each stove specifications
- Account for deforestation
- Adopt standard cookstoves/ fuel naming
- How can safety component be considered as benefits?

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